

Monolithically Integrated Circuits with Optical Injection Locking of Ring Lasers for QKD and QPSK Applications

D. Massela¹, M. Wallace², R. Broeke², F. Diaz¹, and N. Pinto¹

¹AtlanTTic research center, UVigo - Campus Universitario As Lagoas, Spain

²Bright Photonics BV, Netherlands

Abstract— The technique of Optical Injection Locking of integrated ring lasers promises to be a key technology for the improvement of communications bandwidth. However, it is still lacking experimental verification. In this paper, we present two monolithically integrated photonic circuits that experimentally realize optically injection locking of ring lasers. The preliminary circuit characterizations demonstrate the feasibility of these techniques in integrated photonics platforms. These types of circuits pave the way for future applications in Quantum Key Distribution and coherent communication.

1. INTRODUCTION

With the increasing importance of quantum computers and related technologies, that emerged during the last few years, the debate over communications security has also grown. Quantum computers have the potential to break some of the current encryption technologies used on our communication networks, an issue that could cause significant problems in our society. Quantum Key Distribution (QKD), a technique that makes use of quantum properties of light to create secure communications, promises to solve this security problem [1].

At the same time, the ever-increasing demands on data transmission bandwidth make the search for new technical solutions an extensive research topic. New techniques capable of transmitter bandwidth improvements are emerging, especially those involving light modulation devices like lasers. Lasers Optical Injection Locking (OIL) [2] is one of those techniques, that makes it possible to directly modulate a laser, with bandwidths of up to 100GHz [3], being of great interest.

The transmitter's bandwidth can also be increased by multiplexing a large number of channels on the same transmission medium, however, this is not scalable using traditional bulk optics. Photonic Integrated Circuits (PICs), provide a potential solution that can combine a large number of optical components integrated on a single chip and is considered a key technology for overcoming this scalability limitation [4]. Benefits in terms of reduced device sizes and power consumption turn this technology particularly appealing.

QKD transmitters have been realized in several PIC materials, namely Indium Phosphide (InP) and silicon, showing the advantage of integration in terms of stability and miniaturization of transmitters. The work of Sibson et al. [5] describes the integration of a QKD transmitter without the use of modulators and is based on an OIL technique first demonstrated in [6].

In this paper, we present the first experimental OIL realization of a monolithically integrated ring laser system. An extensive study of this type of system has been reported before, but no experimental realization has been shown yet [7, 8, 9]. We demonstrate two different circuits designed for two distinct applications and manufactured using an InP multi project wafer (MPW) run. Using InP material allows us to integrate laser sources on the same chip, which is not possible with other materials like silicon, for example. The first circuit consists of a Distributed Feedback (DFB) Laser that is OIL to a ring laser. This system is primarily intended for QKD purposes, even if it can be used for coherent communication. However, the modulation scheme would be too complex[10].

Our second circuit is realized using two ring lasers that are fed using a Distributed Bragg Reflector (DBR) laser. This circuit has been designed to be a coherent communication transmitter and thus be able to modulate both ring lasers simultaneously. With respect to the circuit presented by Paraiso et al.[10], the use of ring lasers instead of DFB lasers carries some significant advantages. Firstly, the ring lasers don't need to be tuned like in the case of single-mode lasers. And secondly, by OIL a ring laser we ensure the unidirectional emission from it. Consequently, there are no reflections from the slave laser to the master laser, as we get in the DFB case [3].

2. CIRCUIT DESIGN

This section will provide a brief description of the two designed circuits and their components.

2.1. DFB and single ring circuit

The first circuit schematic is presented in figure 1. The notation we present for the ring lasers follows the one used for the mask design, consequently, the ring laser of the first circuit is labelled as *ring 3*. In this circuit, we use a simple DFB laser (master laser) to optically inject a ring laser (slave laser). For the laser source, we used a standard DFB laser module from the InP foundry, designed to emit at $1550nm$, and with the left output terminated using a photodiode. This photodiode, also from the default InP building blocks, will be used to characterize the DFB laser's emitted power. The ring laser is created by using two multimode interferometers (MMI) as couplers. The MMIs used are all 2×2 and the additional unused port is terminated using a photodiode. These photodiodes, will allow the measurement of power circulating inside the ring cavity, in clockwise (CW) and counterclockwise (CCW) directions. These MMIs are customized and designed to split power unequally, as 85% on the cross output and 15% on the bar output. We have chosen this particular ratio to reduce the losses inside the ring and to have a shorter gain section. The photodiodes inside the ring are used to monitor both the clockwise and counterclockwise directed power. The gain section uses a standard InP semiconductor optical amplifier (SOA) that is $400\mu m$ long and has been electrically connected using RF lines. This will allow us to drive the ring laser and verify the modulation bandwidth enhancement due to OIL. A spot size converter is placed at the output of the circuit to minimize the losses when coupling the light output to an external fiber.

Figure 1: This schematic represents the first circuit design of OIL ring laser. The ring laser is injected using a DFB laser. The MMIs and monitoring photodiodes are omitted for simplification. Note the ring label "ring 3" to match the mask notation.

2.2. DBR and double ring circuit

The second circuit is schematized in figure 2, and the two rings are named *ring 1* and *2*. In this case, we exploit the two outputs of a master DBR laser to OIL two slave ring lasers. The main advantage with respect to the first circuit is the ability to use the modulation of each slave ring for encoding the bits of QPSK scheme. The modulation bandwidth is enhanced by the OIL since we are going to modulate the two slave lasers and not the master laser. Additionally, this type of design can also be used for QKD applications, allowing traditional and quantum modulation schemes on the same device. The DBR master laser is built with three standard InP foundry components, namely

Figure 2: This schematic represents the second OIL ring laser design. A DBR laser is used to inject the two ring lasers. The $\pi/2$ phase shifter can be seen in the output of ring 1. The MMIs and photodiodes are omitted.

DBR mirrors with a length of $30\mu m$, a $400\mu m$ SOA and a $200\mu m$ phase modulation section. These parameters ensure that the DBR laser has a high output power. The two outputs of the DBR laser are fed into two slave ring lasers that are identical in dimensions and components to the one from the first circuit. A phase modulator is connected to the output of one slave laser, to obtain the $\pi/2$ phase shift required for QPSK modulation. This additional phase modulation section is made up of a thermo-optical phase modulator of length $450\mu m$, long enough to ensure the $\pi/2$ phase difference between the two rings. The outputs of both slave rings are then combined into a single output, by a 2×1 MMI, followed by a spot size converter.

The two circuits presented in this work are fitted to an InP MPW cell with dimensions $8mm \times 2mm$, highlighting the small footprint of both circuits in comparison to traditional modulator based circuits. The fabricated chip can be seen in figure 3.

Figure 3: Photo of the manufactured circuit under a microscope. The first circuit can be seen on left side, while the second is on the right side of the chip. The metal pads for electrical connections can be seen on the top and bottom of the chip, while the optical connections are done on the left and right sides.

3. MEASUREMENTS AND DISCUSSION

In the following sections, we are going to present the preliminary characterization results of the circuit's basic functionalities.

3.1. DFB and single ring circuit

To verify the DFB laser functionality, we used the coupled photodiode to measure the power response when feeding it with a variable current. When analyzing the emission of the DFB laser it became immediately evident that there had been some problems in the fabrication. The measured threshold is above $60mA$ against the $25mA$ expected from the design manual. We have measured other DFB lasers fabricated in the same MPW run and the threshold current ranges from $44mA$ to $60mA$ with maximum emitted power above $1mW$ only in one case. The observed variability in the component behaviour has been later confirmed by the fabrication report. Aside from that issue, some measurements have been done, but taking into account that the master laser has a performance that deviates from the expected values.

To estimate the ring MMI performances we drove the DFB at $80mA$, resulting in a current at the DFB photodiode of $-80\mu A$ whereas the MMI cross port photodiode registered $-60\mu A$. Both the photodiodes were biased at $-2V$ during the measurement. Assuming a $1dB$ loss for this kind of component we reach the result that the splitting ratio of the MMI is 83% for the cross port and 17% for the through port. This ratio is close to the designed ratio of 85 – 15.

To test the ring laser, we coupled a fiber to the chip and drove the ring3 SOA at $100mA$, obtaining the spectrum of Figure 4. We can notice that in this case, the output is a single mode with lots of small peaks representing the cavity resonances, the frequency comb in the low power regime. The single emission peak is due to cross-gain saturation and to fabrication defects, that lead to internal reflections. The lasing spectrum is not stable and tends to jump, with side modes appearing and disappearing and following non-predictable fluctuations. This is due to the laser's inherent multi-mode nature.

To verify and characterize the OIL of the system, we set a current of $100mA$ to the ring3 SOA and $97mA$ to the DFB master laser. The obtained spectrum can be seen in Figure 5. When comparing both spectra of single ring laser (figure 4) and OIL laser, we can see that the main

Figure 4: Measured spectral response of the laser ring 3, with the SOA driven at $100mA$. The single emission peak is due to cross-gain saturation and fabrication defects. We can notice the frequency comb in the low power regime.

peak is shifted from $1548.1nm$ to $1549.4nm$, while the secondary peak seen in figure 4 at $1545nm$ disappears. This behaviour demonstrates that the system works as expected. To additionally verify that OIL is working, the obtained power at MMIs photodiodes can be used. When in OIL, we measured the current at the MMI's photodiodes to be in CCW direction. The optical injection of a ring laser ensures the unidirectionality of the light inside the cavity, completely suppressing the CW mode. Also, the CW photodiode turned on and off following DFB laser. Without DFB laser injection the ring laser is bidirectional, with the measured current on the CW photodiode being $-0.160mA$. When the DFB laser is turned on at $97mA$, the current measured on the CW photodiode is $-0.002mA$, demonstrating the high suppression of the CW light and the successful OIL.

Figure 5: Spectrum of the ring3 laser powered at $100mA$ when it is injected with the DFB at $97mA$. We can notice the shift in wavelength with respect to figure 4 that is due to the optical injection of the DFB.

3.2. DBR and double ring circuit

To characterize the second circuit, we will start our analysis by running individually the *ring 2* laser. This laser has a similar construction to *ring 1* and *ring 3* from the previous circuit. The

main difference, in this case, is the presence of the DBR mirror feedback from the master laser. This fact changes the behaviour of the ring, giving it a preferred lasing direction.

The measured *ring 2* spectrum is presented in figure 6, which similarly to the *ring 1* laser from the single ring circuit, shows an unstable single peak around $1553.3nm$. It is typical of a multimode laser to change lasing frequency based on small changes in temperature and conditions of the cavity, leading to a highly unstable emission. Small fabrication defects on the mirrors and waveguides can lead to additional reflections and different cavity lengths, respectively, affecting the ring response. Another effect not taken into account is the cross-gain saturation effect that tends to make only a single wavelength lase.

Figure 6: Emission spectra measured at $60mA$ current injection on the *ring 2* SOA. As in the previous case, a single mode peak can be seen with smaller small peaks and the frequency comb

The design of the DBR laser was focused on having a high power output sacrificing the single mode emission. We will use the OIL not only for isolating a single frequency of the slave lasers but also to isolate a single frequency of the DBR master laser. The challenging part will then be to lock both *ring 1* and *ring 2* lasers to the master frequency.

To verify individually the OIL, we first set and measure a single ring. Figure 7 shows the measured output of *ring 1* laser when injected with the DBR laser. The laser emission is single mode at $1550nm$, with a side-mode suppression ratio of $45dB$, demonstrating the locking of the two lasers. In fact, we do not see the multimode emission of the DBR laser nor any sign of the multimode of the ring laser. This shows that this system has effectively achieved OIL, and can be used for QKD like the previous one. Like in the case of the DFB and *ring 3*, the current applied to the SOA is critical and affects the locking mechanism, although we can find multiple combinations of currents that achieve OIL. Considering this single ring setup with DBR.

The next step was to verify if we could simultaneously lock both *ring 1* and *ring 2* to the same DBR laser mode. When the *ring 2* laser is activated we notice that a series of other peaks appear in the spectrum, in addition to the main peak from *ring 1*. In trying to achieve a stable locking of both ring lasers, we have varied the applied current to the different lasers, but even the best outcomes have not been convincing. Additionally, we have decided to vary the phase modulator in the DBR laser in order to check its influence on the locking mechanism. We drove both SOA rings at the same constant current of $80mA$, and varied the currents applied to the DBR laser SOA and phase sections. The best recorded spectrum is visible in figure 8, obtained with $77mA$ on the SOA and $29mA$ on the phase modulator. From the resulting spectrum, we can see a main peak at $1551nm$ and a few side peaks around $35dB$ lower. It is clear that the system is not still locked and the three lasers influence the emission of one another, even if in an OIL system they should be lasing in a single direction as verified for *ring 3*. In fact, if we turn *ring 1* off the output spectrum goes back to being multimode.

Figure 7: Emission spectra of *ring 1* at $55mA$ when injected with the DBR laser at $40mA$. We can notice the single mode emission resulting from the locking of the DBR and the ring.

Further investigation into this system is necessary to understand why the optical injection doesn't work for both rings simultaneously. The photodiodes inside *ring 1* and *ring 2* should be monitored to verify if there is light travelling in the counter propagating mode of the laser.

Figure 8: Measured spectrum, with *ring 1* and *ring 2* SOAs injected at $80mA$, while DBR laser SOA and phase modulators are driven at $77mA$ and $29mA$, respectively. This was the best case achieved while trying to get both lasers locked.

4. CONCLUSION

Throughout this paper, we describe the designs and preliminary characterization results on two OIL-based photonic integrated circuits, with potential applications on QKD and QPSK.

The first circuit presented here is based on a simple and easy to manufacture design, that uses common and widely available components on several InP foundries. We have characterized individually the components, finding some manufacturing problems with our master laser. The custom MMIs operated in close agreement with the designed specifications, achieving the expected splitting ratio. When considering the complete circuit, our characterization results show that it was possible to achieve OIL between the two lasers, resulting in single-mode, single direction emission. This is the

first experimental verification of a monolithically integrated OIL system, using ring lasers. The second circuit, which is based on a double ring laser configuration, also uses common InP components, making it easy to manufacture. However, locking both rings at the same time turned out to be a more complex task. We have characterized one of the ring lasers locked by the DBR laser and we demonstrated that OIL can be achieved, performing as expected. When considering the locking of both ring lasers to the master DBR laser, we achieved only partial locking when using the DBR phase tuning section. These results are clearly still not usable for QPSK, since, for this application, we need a single wavelength. Both rings must be locked for this design to achieve the desired high speed modulation, needed on QPSK modulation schemes. In the future, we plan to further investigate the double ring locking system, which presents some additional challenges to operate properly. Moreover, we want to test and measure the modulation bandwidth of both circuits, as well as evaluate them in QKD applications. Due to the issues found on manufactured lasers, these same designs must be redone in a new MPW run.

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